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“ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF BANKING RISK MANAGEMENT”

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Annotation: *This article discusses issues and solutions and suggestions for improving the risk management efficiency of existing commercial banks. At the same time, ways to improve bank risk management were mentioned.*

Keywords: *banking risk, liquidity, credit, assets, market economy, credit agreement, operational risk.*

In the context of further deepening reforms and modernization of the economy in the country, important tasks are set for commercial banks. At the same time, it is important to effectively organize risk management in banks and increase the stability of the banking system and strengthen public confidence in it. In this regard, further reform of the banking system focuses on improving risk management.

In particular, the Cabinet of Ministers privatized and transformed the joint-stock commercial bank “Uz industrial construction bank” with the participation of the International Finance Corporation (IFC). Resolution No. 161 of March 29, 2021 was adopted. [1] Banks often run the risk of unbalanced liquidity as a result of customer selection mistakes. These risks usually arise when lending to businesses with volatile economies is preferred. Unbalanced liquidity risk is caused by poor management of the bank's management and staff, poor organization of banking supervision, imperfection of methods used to manage risks, setting risk coefficients for individual banking operations or their groups. occurs as a result of deficiencies. Banks need to be careful of the risk of insolvency and inability to continue their financial and economic activities due to lack of funds. If a bank has issued a large amount of loans without a thorough analysis of the loan

application, and there is a possibility that they will not be repaid, such “bad” loans can cause significant damage to the bank. The bank is still exposed to interest rate risk as both the lender and the borrower. An increase in interest rates for the bank as a lender (resources) leads to a decrease in the profit of the bank’s operations. A similar change, an increase in interest rates on borrowed resources, is and the bank suffers. The main problem in managing the bank's assets and liabilities is to prevent or reduce interest rate risk. It is advisable to use the imbalance method. It is advisable to increase interest rate risk management and insurance opportunities in banks. At present, the use of the GAP method of interest rate risk management in the practice of banks in the country is not allowed. The bank does not have a robust manufacturing process to manage credit risks. Common shortcomings include:

- the political comment is not documented;
- no restrictions on portfolio accumulation;
- excessive centralization or decentralization of credit management;
- Lack of good analysis of the lending sector;
- Superficial financial analysis of borrowers;
- Lack of frequent contact with customers;
- Insufficient scrutiny and imbalance in the lending process;
- lack of control over debt;
- inability to increase the cost of credit due to deteriorating credit quality;
- poor control over debt documentation;
- excessive use of borrowed funds;
- incompleteness of credit documents;
- Lack of grouping of assets and standards in the formation of reserves for loan losses;
- Lack of effective control and audit of the credit process. [2]

These shortcomings have contributed to the weakening of the loan portfolio, including the accumulation and stagnation of loans to one sector or the economic sector, large loan portfolios, credit losses, insolvency and insolvency. takes There is no doubt that in many markets, banks operate in such an economic environment that they face objective difficulties in the quality management of loans, which indicates the need to strengthen credit management. At present, most commercial banks in the country do not provide in-depth analysis of the cost of loans. In countries with developed market economies, the market price of a loan is taken into account when determining the price of a loan, but the calculation of the cost of a loan to the customer consists of several steps, and this indicator is calculated by commercial banks. The main purpose of determining the cost of

the loan is to ensure the profitability and liquidity of the bank, while achieving the effectiveness of the loan provided by the bank. This result can help to identify bank risks in advance and prevent them. The current problem of credit risks for banks is that in the presence of credit risk, the lender (bank) is unsure of the ability of the borrower to fulfill the terms of the loan agreement, its obligations in a timely manner. It is known that the main benefit in banking practice is the interest on loans. Failure to repay the interest rate on the borrower or the principal amount of the loan on time or not at all will result in a decrease in the bank's future assets as a result of a decrease in the bank's profits. In general, there are a number of problems in risk management in the banking sector of the country, the elimination of which, the establishment of a modern risk management system based on international standards will serve to further strengthen the stability of the banking system.

In our opinion, it is expedient to improve the effective credit risk management in the risk management system of the country's banks in the following areas:

- Improving the methodology of credit risk assessment in banks. At present, the assessment of creditworthiness in our banks is limited to the use of financial ratios (coverage, liquidity, autonomy). Cash flow analysis, scoring, and internal rating methods should be widely used in risk assessment in banking practice.

- Further improving the quality of the loan portfolio of banks of the Republic. The ratio of special reserves created to cover the losses of the banking system of the country to total bank assets is more than twice. However, the acceptable level should be 0.5%.

- Increasing the level of diversification of the loan portfolio. Today, the loan portfolio of most banks is dominated by the volume of loans allocated to one sector. This indicates that the risk of banks' loan portfolios is growing.

It should be noted that in the risk management system of commercial banks to prevent a significant increase in foreign exchange liabilities, effective management of currency risks plays an important role in ensuring the stability of the bank. The analysis of the loan portfolio of commercial banks of the country shows that in the context of the devaluation of the national currency, the share of foreign currency loans in the total loan portfolio has decreased significantly. In our opinion, the improvement of the practice of regulating the level of operational risk in the activities of banks in the country should be identified as one of the important areas of effective organization of risk management. Analysis of the current methodology for managing the operational risk of the bank's lending activities shows that to date, the country's banking practice has not implemented a comprehensive concept of operational risk management, which includes the systematic identification, measurement and minimization of operational risks. At the same time, in

order to identify operational risks in the activities of commercial banks and to form the necessary database for this purpose, banks should regularly collect information on operating losses, develop a form of reporting on operating losses and regularly review them. they have to go. It should be noted that the database of internal operational risks in banks. [3] Only if you can gather data over a period of 3-5 years will you be able to use them to identify future risks. In our opinion, the following ways to improve the measurement of operational risks in the banking practice of our country can be proposed:

Improving risk measurement by developing qualitative methods of assessment and analysis.

Improve risk measurement by expanding the scope of the assessment. As one of the main operational risks of credit activity, it is advisable to focus on the assessment and analysis of the qualifications of employees and the quality of banking processes.

Additional methods of risk minimization include function outsourcing and process benchmarking. The analysis shows that commercial banks are more likely to outsource (outsource certain functions and business processes to foreign companies specializing in this field) and process benchmarking (constant search for “best practices” in this area). methods are not used sufficiently. [4] However, these methods are widely used in foreign practice and can be recommended for use in our country. It is known that the Committee on Banking Risk Control has been established within the corporate governance of commercial banks, which reports directly to the Board. In our opinion, in order to ensure the effective functioning of this committee, it is advisable to open the following risk management units in each commercial bank:

- Market Risk Management Division;
- Credit Risk Management Division;
- Operational Risk Management Division

The establishment of these divisions will allow to identify significant risks in the banking business and to monitor them on a regular basis.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the timely detection of risks in the activities of banks in the country, the development of measures to reduce them and effective management will further strengthen the financial stability of the banking system. Modern banking is directly related to various risks, and their effective management is one of the most important functions of banks. The risk is different in each banking transaction and is covered in different ways. In a market economy, it is difficult to find risk-free operations that guarantee a pre-determined financial result. It is important for commercial banks not to avoid risk, but to minimize them. The banking risk management system consists of a set of elements that protect the credit institution from the effects of internal and external

threats and act within the framework of the law, representing a certain integrity in the relationship and communication. Risk management in banking should have the following main objectives: to protect the interests of bank depositors and creditors, shareholders, to reduce, eliminate and prevent banking risks, to ensure adequate stability of banking activities.

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